

EARTH QUAKES THAT TRIGGERS TSUNAMIS - AN ASTROLOGICAL STUDY

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Cite This Article: Nittala V. S. R. Krishna Prasad & Dr. Thangavel Murugan, "Earth Quakes that Triggers Tsunamis - An Astrological Study", International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Volume 8, Issue 2, July - December, Page Number 1-4, 2023.

Abstract:

This paper is aimed to examine Earth Quakes that triggers Psunamis in the world in the past and predicting these Earth Quakes if possible to occur in future using the Astrological combinations that are shown.

Key Words: Earth Quakes, Eclipses, Richter scale, Magnitude, Planets, Retrograde, Conjunction, Opposition, Mutual Aspect, Signs & Stars.

Introduction:

Earth Quakes and Psunamis are among the natural calamities that occur in world. In very few cases Earth Quakes with highest magnitude will trigger Tsunamis. If we examine carefully all the Astrological reasons for the incidents in the past we can take all the precautionary measures for saving lives of people.

Methodology:

EQ tsunami
1. Birth chart I

Wed Nov 28,1945 04:56:05 Timezone: -5:30:00 Daylightsaving : 0 Place of birth : Churi PAKISTAN(general) Pakistan Longitude: 72E51'00 Latitude: 31N31'00	Ishtakal : 53:58:32 Sunrise : Nov 27,45 07:20:40 Sunset : Nov 27,45 17:31:26 Ayanamsha : -23:05:47 Lahiri
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Birth Chart	Navamsha (spouse)	Bhava (Sripati)																																																												
<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 25%;">6th h. Aci</td> <td style="width: 25%;">7th h. Yuvati</td> <td style="width: 25%;">8th h. Randira</td> <td style="width: 25%;">9th h. Dharma</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Ra</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>SaR Ma</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Mo</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MeR Ke</td> <td>Su</td> <td>As Ve</td> <td>Ju</td> </tr> </table>	6th h. Aci	7th h. Yuvati	8th h. Randira	9th h. Dharma				Ra				SaR Ma				Mo	MeR Ke	Su	As Ve	Ju	<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 25%;">3rd h. Sabaja</td> <td style="width: 25%;">4th h. Bandira</td> <td style="width: 25%;">5th h. Patra</td> <td style="width: 25%;">6th h. Aci</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>MeR</td> <td>Ve</td> <td>Ke</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>SaR</td> </tr> <tr> <td>As</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Ju</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ra Mo</td> <td></td> <td>Su</td> <td>Ma</td> </tr> </table>	3rd h. Sabaja	4th h. Bandira	5th h. Patra	6th h. Aci		MeR	Ve	Ke				SaR	As			Ju	Ra Mo		Su	Ma	<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 25%;">6th h. Aci</td> <td style="width: 25%;">7th h. Yuvati</td> <td style="width: 25%;">8th h. Randira</td> <td style="width: 25%;">9th h. Dharma</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Ra</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>SaR Ma</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>Mo</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MeR Ke</td> <td>Su</td> <td>As Ve</td> <td>Ju</td> </tr> </table>	6th h. Aci	7th h. Yuvati	8th h. Randira	9th h. Dharma				Ra				SaR Ma				Mo	MeR Ke	Su	As Ve	Ju
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Degree	RC	Nakshatra	Nama	p#,lrd/sb
As 11:48:55		Swati	Ray	2,Ra/Sa
Su 12:16:42		Anuradha	Noo	3,Sa/Ma
Mo 28:22:25		U.Phalg.	Tay	1,Su/Mo
Ma 09:48:45		Pushya	Hay	2,Sa/Ve
Me 00:01:39	R	Moola	Yay	1,Ke/Ke
Ju 26:32:46		Chitra	Pay	1,Ma/Ju
Ve 26:32:44		Vishakha	Too	2,Ju/Ke
Sa 01:22:55	R	Punarvasu	Hee	4,Ju/Ra
Ra 07:10:14		Ardra	Koo	1,Ra/Ra
Ke 07:10:14		Moola	Bha	3,Ke/Ra

Details such as date, time of the incident and place of the earthquakes that triggered Tsunamis are taken and chart is laid down. Other details like magnitude of Earth Quakes, things that are destroyed, deaths of people and all the other information is gathered. Eclipse that is associated is studied fully. And all the other Astrological analysis is done.

Example 1:

- Date & Time: 28th November 1945, 04:56,
- Place: Churi Pakistan
- Magnitude: It is 8.0 on Richter Scale.

This was the major Tsunami generating Earth Quake in the Arabian sea. More than four thousand people were killed on the Makran coast by both Earth Quake and Tsunami. The Tsunami reached a height of Forty feet in some Makran and caused great damage to the entire coastal region. The Tsunami is also recorded in Muscat and Gwadar. The Lagna is Libra. The Lagna Lord is in Lagna. Fourth Lord Saturn is in Retrograde motion with debilitated Mars Tenth aspects Fourth. Saturn is in one degree which signifies disasters. Uranus is in fixed sign (cause for Earth Quakes) Taurus aspects Sun in Second and Moon in Eleventh. Mercury and Uranus are in retrograde motion. Day Lord is Mars and Star lord is Venus (Poorva Phalguni).

Example 2:

- Eclipse: Solar Eclipse
- Date & Time: 09-July-1945, 13:27Hrs,
- Place: Pakistan

Solar Eclipse
1. Birth chart I

Mon Jul 9, 1945 13:27:05 Ishtakal : 16:45:32
 Timezone: -5:30:00 Daylightsaving : 1 Sunrise : Jul 9,45 06:44:52
 Place of birth : Churi PAKISTAN(general) Pakistan Sunset : Jul 9,45 20:42:05
 Longitude: 72E51'00 Latitude: 31N31'00 Ayanamsha : -23:05:30 Lahiri

Birth Chart

7th h. Yuvati	8th h. Randira	9th h. Dhama	10th h. Karma
	Ma	Ve	Ra Mo Sa Su
6th h. Ari			Me
5th h. Putra			Ju
4th h. Bandhu	3rd h. Sahaja	2nd h. Dhama	1st h. Tama
			Ke

Navamsha (spouse)

10th h. Karma	11th h. Labha	12th h. Vyaya	1st h. Tama
Ve	Mo Sa	Su	As
9th h. Dhama	Ra		3rd h. Dhama
8th h. Karandha			3rd h. Sahaja
7th h. Yuvati	6th h. Ari	5th h. Putra	4th h. Bandhu
	Ma Ju	Me	

Bhava (Sripati)

7th h. Yuvati	8th h. Randira	9th h. Dhama	10th h. Karma
	Ma	Ve	Ra Mo Sa Su
6th h. Ari			Me
5th h. Putra			Ju
4th h. Bandhu	3rd h. Sahaja	2nd h. Dhama	1st h. Tama
			Ke

Birth Chart

	Degree	RC	Nakshatra	Nama	p#,lrd/sb
As	18:55:35		Hasta	Nuh	3,Mo/Me
Su	23:35:52		Punarvasu	Koh	2,Ju/Sa
Mo	20:04:12	c	Punarvasu	Kay	1,Ju/Ju
Ma	27:04:16		Krittika	Ah	1,Su/Su
Me	16:08:19		Pushya	Dah	4,Sa/Ju
Ju	28:39:55		U.Phalg.	Tay	1,Su/Ma
Ve	08:34:10		Krittika	Ay	4,Su/Ve
Sa	21:36:03	c	Punarvasu	Kay	1,Ju/Ju
Ra	16:05:58		Ardra	Nga	3,Ra/Ve
Ke	16:05:58		P.Shad.	Boo	1,Ve/Su

rotating earth is influence by the combined gravitational pull of the Moon and Sun. The most careful scientific study does not reveal statistically meaning full correlations of earth quakes occurrence with tidal loading.

Results and Conclusion:

The following inferences are drawn.

- Kala Sarapa yoga,
- Completely damaged Fourth Lords,
- Fixed signs,
- Presence of both the eclipses,
- Influences of watery signs and watery planets,
- Retrograde Uranus ,Neptune ,
- Weak Jupiter (will not be able to save lives of peoples),
- Strength of Kshetra Lagna Lord and Kshetra Lagna.
- Annual Transit results of the country.

Annual transit results of the country are studied every year and, Eclipses, probabilities of Natural calamities should be noted. All the necessary measures are to be taken in advance to prevent losses especially if afflictions are more. Remedies like havan are to be done massively.

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